

Geomorphometric analysis of the *Summit and Ridge* classes of the Geographic Names Information System

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Abstract—This paper reports results from a geosemantic comparison of landforms classified in the Summit and Ridge feature classes in the Geographic Names Information System (GNIS). The comparison is based on a 2D shape analysis of manually delineated polygons produced by USGS staff to correspond to 33,304 Summit and 8,006 Ridge features. Five shape measures were chosen for this specific geomorphometry-based analysis. Univariate and bivariate statistics are first calculated to compare the two feature classes. This is followed by unsupervised learning with k-means cluster analysis to identify two major geomorphometric clusters corresponding to Summit and Ridge features. Although this supports sufficient internal homogeneity to have stable Summit and Ridge feature classes, more than 7,500 (18%) special features were also identified, which were assigned by k-means to the cluster not corresponding to their given GNIS class. These features remain to be analyzed further to decide if GNIS features should be reclassified based on geomorphometric analysis of available polygonal representations.

I. INTRODUCTION

Landforms are dependent features of terrestrial planetary surfaces and are incredibly challenging to delineate because of their indeterminate and vague extents. Delineation of landform objects is intrinsically linked to how they are conceptualized and categorized (especially into linguistic categories) [3,4]. In geosciences, *general geomorphometric* methods for land surface segmentation are preferred. However, the *specific geomorphometry* approach is preferable for cartographic representation and natural language applications because it can support the naïve (commonsense) geography-based description and characterization of terrain in terms of cognitively and culturally salient landform objects.

Research in specific geomorphometry on automated mapping and geospatial and geomorphological characterization of popularly recognized landforms shown on topographic maps is quite limited. Macroscale landforms are important to people and recognized as individual entities, even if their spatial extents are not explicit. In the United States, all such named landforms are found recorded in the Geographic Names Information System (GNIS), the official topographic gazetteer database developed by the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) in cooperation with the U.S. Board on Geographic Names (BGN) [9]. However, more than 2.28 million GNIS features are classified into 63 non-hierarchical, mutually exclusive, broadly scoped feature classes, which were created based on generic terms of the feature names, such as Mount or Canyon, and not as a definitive or scientific classification system [5].

There are two major limitations of most topographic gazetteers, including GNIS. First, they are limited to point feature representation of all features—including landforms. Thus, the two lead authors have established a long-term research collaboration for automating the extraction of cognitively plausible and scale-sensitive areal representations of landforms [1,2,6,7]. Adapting such methods for national-scale automated mapping of GNIS landform features is one of the top objectives of this collaboration.

The second problem of gazetteers is due to basing the classes on name generics, lack of a formal specification of class semantics, and issues of semantic overlap between classes. In the case of landforms within GNIS, there has never been a formal investigation into whether the chosen landform categories make semantic sense or whether features are classified correctly. A visual scan of topographic map labels for specific landforms and

nearby contour patterns reveals cases where the GNIS classification fails to correspond to the type of landform people would identify in that area. A formal, large-area study is only possible if mapped boundaries for landform features are available. However, no existing general or even specific geomorphometric methods yield a cognitively plausible agreement between named landforms as would be visually perceived by people and algorithmically extracted objects.

Fortunately, the authors now have access to a database of manually delineated 2D polygons corresponding to 89,100 GNIS landform features across the US. These polygons were digitized by USGS staff members of the US Topo program [8] for a different project related to the automated placement of feature labels on topographic maps. A small subset of the manually delineated polygons has already been successfully used to identify limitations and suggest improvements for the core-minence method of mapping salient topographic eminences (a subset of convex landforms) [6].

The discussion here is limited to the semantic comparison of the *Summit* and *Ridge* feature classes based on the 2D shape analysis of manually delineated polygons corresponding to GNIS landform features from the classes. *Summit* and *Ridge* features correspond, respectively, to non-linear and linear topographic eminences, which are cognitively salient convex landforms [7].

II. METHODOLOGY

GNIS point feature data are freely available as a text file from the USGS [9]. Manually digitized GNIS landform polygons were obtained internally by the second author by virtue of her status as a USGS employee. This dataset is not available publicly. Of the 89,100 landform polygons, 33,304 correspond to *Summit* and 8,006 to *Ridge* GNIS landform features. The 2D shape analysis of these *Summit* and *Ridge* landform polygons relied on five popular 2D shape measures summarized in Table 1. For the *elongation* measure, the width and length of the oriented bounding box for each GNIS feature were generated with the help of the *Minimum Bounding Geometry* tool available in ArcGIS Pro GIS software. All other shape measures were calculated with the help of the Python *shapely* package, widely used for the manipulation and analysis of planar geometric objects.

Univariate statistics, box plots, and frequency distribution histograms were generated for each shape measure to summarize shape measure statistics. Next, a bivariate scatterplot and correlation matrix was generated for all pairs of shape measures to thoroughly analyze the shape differences between features within and across the *Summit* and *Ridge* classes.

TABLE I. 2D OBJECT SHAPE MEASURES

2D Shape Measure	Shape Description	
	Formula	Definition
Compactness (Com)	$(4\pi \cdot \text{area}) / (\text{perimeter})^2$	Ratio of the area of an object to the area of a circle with the same perimeter. <i>Max value of 1 is achieved for circular objects.</i>
Roundness (Rou)	$(4\pi \cdot \text{area}) / (\text{convex perimeter})^2$	Ratio of the area of an object to the area of a circle with the same perimeter as the object's convex hull. <i>Max value of 1 is achieved for circular objects.</i>
Elongation (Elo)	(width / length)_bb	The width-to-length ratio of the object's bounding box is oriented parallel to the object's major axis.
Convexity (Con)	(convex perimeter) / (object perimeter)	Ratio of the perimeter of an object's convex hull to the perimeter of the object itself. <i>A value of 1 signifies a perfectly convex object, and a value less than one signifies an object having an irregular boundary or containing holes.</i>
Solidity (Sol)	(object area) / (convex area)	Ratio of the perimeter of an object's convex hull to the perimeter of the object itself. <i>A value of 1 signifies a solid object, and a value less than one signifies an object having an irregular boundary or containing holes.</i>

Finally, all 41,310 features were input into the unsupervised machine learning method of K-means cluster analysis to test if 2D shape measures segregated the features into only two or more statistically significant clusters. Testing was done by deriving up to 10 clusters to check for the existence of additional transitional classes in addition to the expected two primary clusters corresponding to *Summit* and *Ridge* classes. Features (mis)classified by the K-means method such that *Summit* (*Ridge*) features assigned to the cluster corresponding to the other *Ridge* (*Summit*) feature class were identified and analyzed for more insights.

All data analysis and K-means cluster analysis were automated with a Python script using typically used Python data analysis and visualization libraries.

III. RESULTS

A. Geomorphometric analysis based on exploratory statistics

As evident from summary statistics (Table 1) and the frequency distributions (Figure 1), the shape measures help capture differences between the shapes of polygons digitized for the GNIS *Summit* and *Ridge* feature classes. Note that because *compactness* and *roundness* are strongly positively correlated (Figure 2) and have nearly identical frequency distributions, only the frequency distribution for *Roundness* is included in Figure 1. *Ridge* shape measure distributions are close to normal, but *Summit* shape measures are all left-skewed, with extremely

skewed solidity and convexity. Based on the mean values of shape measures and distribution shapes, the digitized polygons would lead us to believe that. In contrast, there is substantial overlap between shape-measure frequency distributions; non-linear *Summit* features are more rounded, less elongated, and exhibit a higher degree of solidity/convexity than *Ridge* features. Box plots (not presented here for lack of space) also complemented these observations.

The correlation matrix in Figure 2 shows the direction and strength of correlation between all five shape measures. As expected, *compactness* is significantly positively correlated with *roundness*. But they still differ appreciably in the power of their correlations with other variables. Both *compactness* and *roundness* are positively correlated with all other measures as well, but most positively with *solidity*. In contrast, *elongation* exhibits its weakest correlations with *convexity*, followed by *solidity*, with these correlations being appreciably lower for the *Ridge* feature class compared to the *Summit* class. For only *Ridge* features, there is also an interesting lack of correlation between *roundness* and *convexity* (but not *solidity*). Scatter plots of all variable pairs (not shown here) confirmed insights already gained.

B. Geomorphometric analysis based on K-Means clusters

The K-means unsupervised method was chosen because this project aimed to identify clusters representing *Summit* and *Ridge* objects. When the five shape measures for the 41,310 features were input into the k-means algorithm, it predicted only two primary clusters. A sharp elbow (inflection point) was observed after two clusters in the inertia plot. Due to the predominance of *Summit* features in one cluster and *Ridge* features in another, the clusters can also be confidently assumed to correspond mainly to GNIS *Summit* and *Ridge* feature classes.

Table II reports the means for all shape measures for the four sets of features derived from a combination of two original GNIS feature classes and two predicted clusters. It seems clear that *Summit* or *Ridge* features assigned to the corresponding majority *Summit* or *Ridge* cluster, respectively, are characterized by substantially larger shape measure values than features assigned to the non-corresponding (*Summit* to *Ridge*, *Ridge* to *Summit*) cluster.

The K-means clustering accuracy analysis presented in Table III reveals that 98% of features in one cluster are *Summit* and 94% in another are *Ridge* features, indicating that data-driven clusters correspond strongly to GNIS *Summit* and *Ridge* feature classes. The most interesting finding from K-means analysis is the identification of 7,171 (21.5%) GNIS *Summit* and 475 (6%) GNIS *Ridge* features that were morphometrically more similar to features in the *Ridge* and *Summit* cluster, respectively.

Figure 1. Frequency distributions for *roundness*, *elongation*, *solidity*, and *convexity* shape measures for *Summit* and *Ridge* classes.

Figure 2. Correlation matrix summarizing correlations between shape measures for *Summit* and *Ridge* feature classes.

As mentioned above, the means of shape measures are already much smaller for these minority features. The reason became apparent when the manually digitized polygons for these minority *Summit* and *Ridge* features were overlaid on USGS topographic maps (available as a basemap in ArcGIS Pro). Figure 3 shows example polygons for each type of minority feature. Whereas the minority *Summit* features are long and narrow, the minority *Ridge* features are not linear but shaped more like rounded/compact *Summit* features. The manual polygons are digitized based on labels found on topographic maps. The importance of generic parts of feature names played a

vital role in originally classifying GNIS features. Still, the analysis here reveals that the choice of generic terms is not always reliable as an indicator of the geomorphometric characteristics of a feature. This will always present challenges in determining the semantic scope of GNIS feature classes. Indeed, the k-means algorithm performed admirably to isolate more than 7,500 of such specialized cases requiring more careful analysis of their shapes and possible reassignment to the other feature classes.

IV. CONCLUSION

This analysis clearly shows that the specific geomorphometry approach to GNIS enhancement can help guide the automation of feature extraction for both named and unnamed prominent landforms in the United States and other countries. Although descriptive statistics and K-means cluster analysis confirmed the usefulness of the chosen shape measures, the analysis presented herein is still limited and exploratory. Future work could reduce the correlation between shape measures and test transformations to reduce the skewness of some shape measures before statistically valid hypotheses about if and how GNIS features could be reclassified based on geomorphometric analysis of available polygonal representations, especially to use as training data in deep learning. The authors have also initiated work to understand whether (dis)similarities in shapes of features can be related to the generic terms in their names. A more comprehensive set of findings will be presented in a forthcoming journal paper, including more robust evidence based on inferential statistics.

TABLE II. MEAN STATISTICS FOR SHAPE MEASURES

GNIS		Count	Mean statistics for Shape measures				
			Com	Rou	Sol	Con	Elo
Summit		33,304	0.66	0.69	0.91	0.97	0.60
Ridge		8,006	0.28	0.34	0.67	0.91	0.27
GNIS	K-means						
Summit	Summit	26,133	0.73	0.75	0.95	0.99	0.65
Summit	Ridge	7,171	0.37	0.46	0.75	0.90	0.41
Ridge	Ridge	7,531	0.26	0.32	0.66	0.91	0.26
Ridge	Summit	475	0.61	0.64	0.92	0.97	0.44

TABLE III. K-MEANS CLUSTER ANALYSIS RESULTS

Confusion Matrix			Accuracy Analysis		
GNIS	K-Means Cluster		TP = True positive	FP = False positive	Total
	(Summit) Cluster	(Ridge) Cluster	TN = True negative	FN = False negative	
			Precision TP / (TP + FP)	Recall TP / (TP + FN)	
Summit	26,133	7,171	0.98	0.78	33,304
Ridge	475	7,531	0.51	0.94	8,006
Overall Accuracy: 0.81					41,310

Figure 3. (Left) Examples of *Summit* features assigned by K-means to the cluster mostly dominated by *Ridge* features. (Right) Examples of *Ridge* features assigned by K-means to the cluster dominated by *Summit* features.

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REFERENCES

- Arundel, S. T., Sinha, G., 2019. Validating the use of object-based image analysis to map commonly recognized landform features in the United States. *Cartography and Geographic Information Science*, 46(5), 441–455.
- Joly, G., Sinha, G., Hassan, W., 2022. Evaluating methods for automated mapping of apexes of non-linear eminences. *Proceedings of the AutoCarto 2022 – 24th International Research Symposium on Cartography and GIScience*.
- Mark, D. M., and Smith, B., 2002. Do mountains exist? Towards an ontology of landforms. *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design*, 30(3), 411–427.
- Minár, J., and Evans, I. S., 2008. Elementary forms for land surface segmentation: the theoretical basis of terrain analysis and geomorphological mapping. *Geomorphology* 95 (3–4): 236–59.
- Orth, D. J., and Payne, R. L., 1987. The National Geographic Names Data Base: Phase II Instructions. *US Geological Survey Circular* 1011.
- Sinha G., and Arundel, S. T., 2021. Automated extraction of areal extents for GNIS Summit features using the Eminence-Core Method. *Proceedings of the Geomorphometry 2020 Conference*.
- Sinha, G., Arundel S. T., Hahmann, T., Stewart, K., Usery, E. L., and Mark, D. M., 2018. The Landform Reference Ontology (LFRO): A foundation for exploring linguistic and geospatial conceptualization of landforms. In: *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Geographic Information Science (GIScience 2018)*, LIPICS Vol. 114.
- USGS 2023a. US Topo: Maps for America. <https://www.usgs.gov/programs/national-geospatial-program/us-topo-maps-america>. Last accessed April 28, 2023.
- USGS 2023b. Geographic Names Information System (GNIS). <https://www.usgs.gov/tools/geographic-names-information-system-gnis>. Last accessed April 28, 2023.